

Efficient Time Share Masking of AES

Subhadeep Banik¹ and Francesco Regazzoni^{1,2}

¹ Università della Svizzera Italiana, Lugano, Switzerland. subhadeep.banik@usi.ch

² University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam, Netherlands. f.regazzoni@uva.nl

Abstract. Time sharing was a novel approach to small area and low latency first-order masking in hardware presented by Kumar S.V. et al. at IACR TCHES 2024. The principal underlying idea behind the approach was to separate the processing of shares in the time domain in order to achieve non-completeness. The authors used this approach to construct masked round-based implementations of the PRINCE and AES-128 block ciphers which were considerably smaller than state of the art.

In this paper, we observe that the cost in terms of number of gates and amount of random bits required for the time sharing approach is considerably smaller, if the algebraic degree of the underlying S-box is small. Using the well known decomposition of the inverse power map, (i.e. $f(x) = x^{254}$ over $GF(2^8)$ as $f(x) = x^{26} \circ x^{49}$) we present a more efficient approach to mask the AES S-box that requires much lower gate area and randomness to implement and only 2 additional clock cycles. Using this technique we present three implementations of AES-128: **(a)** Bit-Serial, **(b)** Byte-Serial and **(c)** Round based circuit, all of which require much lower gate area and randomness to construct. We present synthesis results from three different Standard Cell libraries to validate our results.

1 Introduction

Over the years, Side-channel attacks have become an increasingly important tool in the cryptographic community. Power analysis has been particularly effective partly because the equipment required to mount such attacks are not particularly sophisticated or expensive. In differential power analysis [KJJ99] (DPA) and its generalizations [BCO04, MS16], an attacker observes the power consumption traces of a cryptographic implementation and applies statistical analysis to infer the underlying secret. Cryptographic literature has also seen a number of countermeasures proposed to protect circuits against such power attacks. Masking is one such approach which uses secret sharing to randomize input and intermediate values within a circuit. To standardize the designing of secure masked circuits, Threshold Implementations (TI) were introduced which provide provable security with respect to side-channel attacks [BGN⁺14, DNR19, NRS11]. When implemented in hardware, a TI is secure even in the presence of glitches, an inherent side effect not considered in earlier schemes [ISW03]. TI comes with enormous overheads in terms of implementation area, particularly when the algebraic degree of the function to be masked is high. It is known that for a degree d function, a secure TI circuit requires at least $d + 1$ shares, increasing

the hardware requirement proportionally with increase in degree. Apart from this several techniques such Consolidating Masking Schemes (CMS) [RBN⁺15], and Domain Oriented Masking (DOM) [GMK16], Generic low latency masking (GLM) [GIB18] and Generic hardware private circuits (GHPC) [KSM20] have been proposed to securely mask hardware in the presence of glitches.

1.1 Time Share Masking

Time Share Masking (TSM) was a generic technique introduced in [VDB⁺24] to mask S-boxes by separating out in time, the processing of shares. This method secures any vectorial Boolean function against first-order attacks and uses only a single register stage, thus executes in a single clock cycle. Every function is masked using two additive shares. In the first cycle, the first share is processed and re-masked and carried over using a register stage to the second cycle along with the second share. In the second cycle all cross-product terms involving the two shares are computed and furthermore all such terms are combined to give the final result. The authors also showed that the method is first-order probing secure and that it is, moreover, composable first-order secure in the Probe-Isolating Non-Interference (PINI) framework by Cassiers et al. [CS20]. This security notion is particularly important since it allows for the composition between gadgets without the need to place additional registers between them.

1.2 Contribution and Organization

In this paper, we make a crucial observation that it becomes increasingly difficult to securely mask S-boxes with higher degree functions. This makes S-boxes like the one used in AES difficult to mask since its algebraic degree is 7. Starting with an observation made in [WMM20] that the inverse power map over $GF(2^8)$ can be decomposed as the composition of lower degree power maps $x \rightarrow x^{26}$ and $x \rightarrow x^{49}$, we first show that the AES S-box can be masked using much lower gate area and random bits as compared to the figures reported in [VDB⁺24]. Next we try to use this masked S-box to create low area implementations of AES-128. We target three design philosophies: **(a) Bit-Serial** We design a bit-serial AES-128 circuit that takes $131 \times 11 = 1441$ cycles to complete every an encryption operation and occupies around 12 kGE in hardware, **(b) Byte-Serial** We design a byte-serial AES-128 circuit that takes $20 \times 11 = 220$ cycles to complete every an encryption operation and occupies around 14 kGE in hardware, and **(c) Round based** We design a round based AES-128 circuit that takes $3 \times 11 = 33$ cycles to complete every an encryption operation and occupies around 177 kGE in hardware.

We benchmark the circuits using three standard cell libraries. The rest of the paper is organized in the following manner. Section 2 introduces the introductory notions of Time Sharing and some related mathematics required to read the paper. In Section 3, we describe in detail our construction of the time shared AES s-box. Sections 4, 5 and 6 describe the three implementations. Section 7 presents all the simulation results from the synthesis of the circuits so designed. Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 Preliminaries

We give a brief introduction to the theory of time share masking. In order to do so seamlessly, we borrow some of the symbols and terminology that originally appeared in [VDB⁺24]. Let $x \in \mathbb{F}_2^k$ be a k -bit word, where its two-share Boolean masking is denoted as $(a, b) \in \mathbb{F}_2^{2k}$ with $a \oplus b = x$. We denote the individual bits of a, b, x as $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}, b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{k-1}, x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{k-1}$, with $a_i \oplus b_i = x_i$ for all i . Consider the monomial $x_0 x_1 x_2 = (a_0 \oplus b_0)(a_1 \oplus b_1)(a_2 \oplus b_2)$. We have that

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 x_1 x_2 &= (a_0 \oplus b_0)(a_1 \oplus b_1)(a_2 \oplus b_2) \\ &= a_0 a_1 a_2 \oplus a_0 a_1 b_2 \oplus a_0 b_1 a_2 \oplus a_0 b_1 b_2 \oplus \\ &\quad b_0 a_1 a_2 \oplus b_0 a_1 b_2 \oplus b_0 b_1 a_2 \oplus b_0 b_1 b_2 \quad \textcircled{1} \\ &= \sum_{v \in \mathbb{F}_2^k} \prod_{v_i=0} a_i \cdot \prod_{v_i=1} b_i \quad \textcircled{2} \end{aligned}$$

Note that there are 8 terms in the expression marked by $\textcircled{1}$, each corresponding to one element in the canonical listing of all the 3 bit strings over a binary alphabet. Thus the expression $\textcircled{2}$ immediately follows. The main idea in TSM is to compute all the monomials $\prod_{v_i=0} a_i$ in the first clock cycle and in the second cycle compute the terms $\prod_{v_i=1} b_i$ and combine them to get the final result.

Indeed the above process is to be repeated for all monomials present in the algebraic expression of the S-box. In general for an arbitrary Boolean function $f : \mathbb{F}_2^k \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_2 : (x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{k-1}) \rightarrow f(x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{k-1})$, of algebraic degree d , we can generalize the above to write

$$f(a \oplus b) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} g_{\pi(I)}(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{k-1}) \cdot h_{\pi(I)}(b_0, b_1, \dots, b_{k-1})$$

In the above expression, $\mathcal{P}_{k,d}$ denotes all binary strings of length k with hamming weight less than or equal to d (or equivalently all sets of cardinality at most d in $[0, k-1]$). This is because if the algebraic degree is bounded by d , we do not need to construct higher degree monomials. g_j, h_j are functions over the shares a, b respectively, which are essentially monomials of degree upto d . And the strings in $\mathcal{P}_{k,d}$ are numbered and indicated by the function π .

The above sharing scheme needs further randomness for security, and so the authors of [VDB⁺24] update the expression as follows

$$f(a \oplus b) = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} (g_{\pi(I)} + r_{\pi(I)}) \cdot h_{\pi(I)} \oplus \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} r_{\pi(I)} \cdot h_{\pi(I)}$$

Finally the two output shares are computed as

$$F_0 = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} (g_{\pi(I)} + r_{\pi(I)}) \cdot h_{\pi(I)}, \quad F_1 = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} r_{\pi(I)} \cdot h_{\pi(I)}$$

Fig. 1: An overview of Time Share Masking Circuit

2.1 Circuit for TSM

Figure 1 presents a brief overview of the circuit of a TSM S-box. We briefly take the reader through the steps involved.

Step 1: Initial Refreshing: We refresh the input shares with initial randomness to get $a' = a \oplus r'$ and $b' = b \oplus r'$. This requires a total of k bits of randomness.

Step 2: Compute all g_j : We now compute all the functions g_j over a' and mask them with additional randomness to get $g_j \oplus r_j$. Essentially this implies that we have to construct all monomials of degree up to d in a' . Define $\binom{k}{\downarrow d} = \sum_{\ell=1}^d \binom{k}{\ell}$. Then this step requires $\binom{k}{\downarrow d}$ bits of randomness.

Step 3: Carry forward to next clock cycle: We use register stages to carry forward the following signals: (a) All the functions $g_j \oplus r_j$ computed so far, (b) All the bits of randomness r_j used so far and (c) the share b' that has been unused at this point of time. This would require a total of $2\binom{k}{\downarrow d} + k$ flip-flops.

Step 4: Compute the functions h_j : In the next clock cycle we compute the functions h_j .

Step 5: Compute F_0 : This is done by evaluating $F_0 = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} (g_{\pi(I)} + r_{\pi(I)}) \cdot h_{\pi(I)}$.

Step 5: Compute F_1 : This is done by evaluating $F_1 = \sum_{I \in \mathcal{P}_{k,d}} r_{\pi(I)} \cdot h_{\pi(I)}$. Note that we now have $F_0 \oplus F_1 = f(a' \oplus b')$. Since $a' \oplus b' = a \oplus b$, the output shares are mathematically correct.

It can be seen that we need $\mathbf{F} = 2\binom{k}{\downarrow d} + k$ flip-flops and a total of $\mathbf{R} = \binom{k}{\downarrow d} + k$ bits of randomness. For the AES and PRINCE S-boxes $d = k - 1$, and so the above expressions boil down to $\mathbf{F} = 2^{k+1} + k - 4$ and $\mathbf{R} = 2^k + k - 2$. However we can see that for smaller d the cost in terms of randomness and flip-flops is considerably lesser, not to mention the circuit savings for constructing g_j, h_j .

3 Masked S-box

It is well known that the AES S-box is constructed by composing an affine transformation over the inverse map $x \rightarrow x^{254}$ over $GF(2^8)$. It is also well known that the algebraic degree of the power map $x \rightarrow x^p$ over any field of characteristic 2, is exactly the hamming weight of p . Since $\text{HW}(254) = 7$, the algebraic degree of the AES S-box is 7. It was shown in [WMM20], that the inverse power map over $GF(2^8)$ can be written as the composition of the power maps $x \rightarrow x^{26}$ and $x \rightarrow x^{49}$. Indeed since $[x^{26}]^{49} = x^{26 \times 49 \bmod 255} = x^{254}$. Now we have that $\text{HW}(26) = \text{HW}(49) = 3$, and so these smaller power maps are essentially cubic S-boxes over 8-bit inputs. Thus if we were to construct the TSM S-box of AES in 2 stages, i.e.

- Stage 1:** Construct the TSM S-box for the power map $x \rightarrow x^{26}$ and then
Stage 2: Construct the TSM S-box for the power map $x \rightarrow x^{49}$ and construct the circuit for the affine map,

then we may hope for some savings in both circuit area and randomness, at the cost of additional time. The cost for constructing a degree 7 S-box for 8-bit inputs is given by $\mathbf{F}_7 = 2^9 + 8 - 4 = 516$ flip-flops and $\mathbf{R}_7 = 2^8 + 8 - 2 = 262$ bits of randomness. Now consider the same costs for a cubic S-box: we have $\mathbf{F}_3 = 2\binom{8}{\downarrow 3} + 8 = 202$ and $\mathbf{R}_3 = \binom{8}{\downarrow 3} + 8 = 100$. Even when we need to double the costs for constructing two successive power maps, we have that $2 \times \mathbf{F}_3 < \mathbf{F}_7$ and $2 \times \mathbf{R}_3 < \mathbf{R}_7$. Even the costs of designing the other parts of the circuit are considerably lower even we have to duplicate them to construct two power maps.

Fig. 2: An overview of Decomposed and Masked AES S-box

3.1 Circuit

Figure 2 shows the construction of the masked AES S-box. We construct the TSM circuits for the individual cubic power maps separately and add the affine transform in the end. The circuit takes 3 cycles to compute the S-box. We synthesized the S-box using three standard cell libraries: (a) Nangate 15 nm OCL, (b) TSMC 65 nm and (c) UMC 40 nm. The results are tabulated in Table 1. We

#	Architecture	Area (μm^2) (GE)		#Random Bits	#Cycles	Power (mW)	Energy (pJ)
Nangate 15 nm							
1	Original [VDB ⁺ 24]	3110.5	15821	262	1	0.4086	40.86
2	Decomposed (This work)	1608.3	8180	200	3	0.1400	42.00
TSMC 65 nm							
3	Original [VDB ⁺ 24]	20852.3	14481	262	1	0.8444	84.44
4	Decomposed (This work)	10488.6	7284	200	3	0.4123	123.69
UMC 40 nm							
5	Original [VDB ⁺ 24]	7960.5	14505	262	1	0.5361	53.61
6	Decomposed (This work)	4057.7	7394	200	3	0.1927	57.81

Table 1: Synthesis results for the decomposed and undecomposed AES S-boxes. Note that power has been evaluated at 10 MHz.

compare the results with the original TSM S-box that appeared in [VDB⁺24], and whose source code is available online at [tsm]. We used the `compile_ultra` directive with the Synopsys Design Compiler to arrive at the results. A timing analysis is then performed on the synthesized netlist using sufficient number of randomly generated test vectors, which outputs the switching statistic of every node in the circuit. This information is used by the Synopsys Power Compiler software to estimate the average power consumed by the circuit. Energy is computed as the product of the average power and the total physical time taken for the circuit to execute a given operation. The synthesis results confirm, that for all the three libraries the decomposed S-box is around 50% smaller than the original S-box reported in [VDB⁺24], while the energy consumption is slightly higher but of the same order as the original S-box.

3.2 Can we do better?

One question the reader may have is why we stopped after decomposing the AES S-box into two smaller cubic power maps. Is it not possible to decompose the S-box further: may be into three/four quadratic power maps that would have resulted in more savings in area/randomness? The short answer is no. It is impossible to decompose the inverse power map further using quadratic power maps, at least over $GF(2^8)$. To find the reason for this, one has to delve into the cyclotomic coset structure mod 255, and define a particular operation between

two cosets. This operation gives the set of cosets a group structure. However the coset arithmetic over $GF(2^8)$ is such that not all the cosets are part of this group. In particular all the cosets that have hamming weight two are outside the group structure, and the hamming weight 3,7 cosets are inside the group. Which is why it is not possible to combine any number of hamming weight 2 cosets to reach the coset in which 254 lies. Since this is of only mathematical interest, we give a more complete detailed analysis in Appendix B.

4 Bit Serial Circuit

One of the main objectives of designing a smaller masked S-box, is to see if one can implement a smaller masked implementation of the AES-128 block cipher, and this was the next objective. The smallest implementations of unmasked AES-128 are those reported in [BCB21, JMPS17]. We chose to pursue the implementation in [BCB21], which only takes 128 cycles per round and $128 \times 11 = 1408$ cycles to compute the entire encryption. This is theoretically the lowest possible for a bit-serial circuit that advances only one bit per clock cycle. Initially our aim was to design the masked circuit also in 128 cycles per round. However unlike [BCB21], in which the S-box is a purely combinatorial circuit, we could not fit all operations in the pipeline if we budgeted for only 128 cycles per round. In stead, since the S-box takes 3 cycles, we found a working solution at 131 cycles per round.

Figure 3 presents an overview of the circuit we use to construct the 131 cycle per round masked circuit (note that we show the datapath for only one of the shares for ease of representation). The circuit closely resembles the 128-cycle per round implementation presented in [BCB21] but with some differences. In the following we present the salient features of the circuit vis-a-vis the [BCB21] circuit.

- (A) Three additional flip-flops:** We need the extra storage elements in the pipeline to accommodate seamlessly a 131 cycle round. Note that the plaintext and key enter bit by bit through the top left corner of the state and key datapaths as shown in Figure 4.
- (B) S-box Operations:** Consider an up-counter t modulo 131 that controls the data movement. At all $t \equiv 7 \pmod{8}$, data is fed into the S-box via the register locations 124 to 130 and the signal on the wire leading to FF 130. At $t \equiv 2 \pmod{8}$ (with $t > 8$) the S-box output is written back to the flip-flops 120 to 127.
- (C) Swaps in the state pipeline:** Swapping bits are performed by placing multiplexers in the circuit. We keep the original placement of multiplexers in the circuit (with one exception). Only the intervals in which a swap is activated are moved forward by 3 clock cycles, i.e. we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{swap}(80, 112) & \text{ at } t \in [59, 66] \cup [91, 98] \cup [123, 130] \cup [8, 15] \\ \text{swap}(56, 120) & \text{ at } t \in [91, 98] \cup [123, 130] \cup [0, 7] \\ \text{swap}(25, 121) & \text{ at } t \in \{130\} \cup [0, 7] \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 3: The bit-serial AES circuit. Note that we show circuit for only one share for ease of representation.

(D) Sequential Mixcolumn: The whole reason of scheduling the swaps in this manner is to make sure that the correct state bits are available as input to the Mixcolumns circuit. Note that we use a sequential version of the Mixcolumn circuit, first introduced in [JMPS17]. In order for the circuit to work correctly, the first 2 bits of each byte must be present at FFs 0,1,8,9,16,17,24,25 at the beginning of each Mixcolumn cycle. We will see that this holds for all the 8 clock cycles: bits at position $t, t + 1$ must be in place for the circuit to work correctly at time t .

Mixcolumn operations are carried out at $t \in [0, 7] \cup [32, 39] \cup [64, 71] \cup [96, 103]$. The circuit is explained pictorially in Fig 4. It may appear a little complicated, but one can understand it thus: in the 0th cycle, the MSB of each byte of the column is stored in the column of FFs marked MSB. This is important because the MSB controls multiplication by 2, 3 in $GF(2^8)$. As shown in the figure, let us call the four signals after the first set of NAND gates (from right to left) Fsig, the second set of NAND gates Bsig and the first set of XOR gates Xsig. Note that these are 4-bit signals indexed from 3 to 0 from top to bottom as they appear in the figure. notLSB is a signal that is always 1 except in the last cycle i.e. at $t = 7, 39, 71, 103$. Poly is a signal that encodes the irreducible polynomial used to extend $GF(2)$ to $GF(2^8)$: it is 0 at cycles 0,1,2,5 otherwise 1.

	Index	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Fsig	3	1	1	1	$1 + a_0$	$1 + a_0$	1	$1 + a_0$	$1 + a_0$
	2	1	1	1	$1 + b_0$	$1 + b_0$	1	$1 + b_0$	$1 + b_0$
	1	1	1	1	$1 + c_0$	$1 + c_0$	1	$1 + c_0$	$1 + c_0$
	0	1	1	1	$1 + d_0$	$1 + d_0$	1	$1 + d_0$	$1 + d_0$
Bsig	3	$1 + a_1$	$1 + a_2$	$1 + a_3$	$1 + a_4$	$1 + a_5$	$1 + a_6$	$1 + a_7$	1
	2	$1 + b_1$	$1 + b_2$	$1 + b_3$	$1 + b_4$	$1 + b_5$	$1 + b_6$	$1 + b_7$	1
	1	$1 + c_1$	$1 + c_2$	$1 + c_3$	$1 + c_4$	$1 + c_5$	$1 + c_6$	$1 + c_7$	1
	0	$1 + d_1$	$1 + d_2$	$1 + d_3$	$1 + d_4$	$1 + d_5$	$1 + d_6$	$1 + d_7$	1
Xsig	3	$a_1 + b_0$	$a_2 + b_1$	$a_3 + b_2$	$a_0 + a_4 + b_3$	$a_0 + a_5 + b_4$	$a_6 + b_5$	$a_0 + a_7 + b_6$	$a_0 + b_7$
	2	$b_1 + c_0$	$b_2 + b_1$	$b_3 + c_2$	$b_0 + b_4 + c_3$	$b_0 + b_5 + c_4$	$b_6 + c_5$	$b_0 + b_7 + c_6$	$b_0 + c_7$
	1	$c_1 + d_0$	$c_2 + d_1$	$c_3 + d_2$	$c_0 + c_4 + d_3$	$c_0 + c_5 + d_4$	$c_6 + d_5$	$c_0 + c_7 + d_6$	$c_0 + d_7$
	0	$d_1 + a_0$	$d_2 + a_1$	$d_3 + a_2$	$d_0 + d_4 + a_3$	$d_0 + d_5 + a_4$	$d_6 + a_5$	$d_0 + d_7 + a_6$	$d_0 + a_7$

Let a, b, c, d be the bytes incident at the Mixcolumn circuit. The above encoding means that Fsig equals "1111" at cycles 0,1,2,5, and " $1 + a_0, 1 + b_0, 1 + c_0, 1 + d_0$ " otherwise. Bsig equals " $1 + a_{t+1}, 1 + b_{t+1}, 1 + c_{t+1}, 1 + d_{t+1}$ " at all cycles except for the last cycle when it equals "1111". And then we have $Xsig = Fsig + Bsig + Rotleft(a_t, b_t, c_t, d_t)$. the above table gives the expressions for Xsig, Fsig, Bsig at all the 8 clock cycles. After that it is easy to check that $[MC3, MC2, MC1, MC0] = Xsig + Rotleft(Xsig) + Rotright(a_t, b_t, c_t, d_t)$ correctly computes the bit level expressions of all the four Mixcolumn outputs at all the 8 clock cycles. After this computation, MC3 is added to the next roundkeybit and cycled back to the state pipeline. The remaining outputs MC2, MC1, MC0 are written back to FFs 7,15,23.

(E) Arrangement of Swaps: As we have seen, for the Mixcolumn circuit to function correctly, at all the 8 cycles bits at locations $t, t + 1$ must be at the correct location i.e. FFs 0,1,8,9,16,17,24,25. If we run a simple script (like the one listed in Appendix A) to see if the sequence of swaps given in **(C)** produces the correct sequence of bits at the above FFs at all the Mixcolumn cycles i.e. $t \in [0, 7] \cup [32, 39] \cup [64, 71] \cup [96, 103]$. We find that swaps generally produce the correct sequence of bits with a few exceptions. Only at $t \in [0, 7]$ the bit at the second position is not present in FF 25. The required bit is however stored at FF 121. So at cycle 0 to 7 we need an extra multiplexer to bring this bit into the Mixcolumn circuit.

To give a clearer picture, note that the first AES Mixcolumn operation requires as input the bytes indexed 0,5,10,15, i.e. (bits $0 \rightarrow 7, 40 \rightarrow 47, 80 \rightarrow 87, 120 \rightarrow 127$). So, we need that the state bits at $t = 0$ at FFs 0,1, 8,9, 16,17, 24,25 be those indexed by 0,1, 40,41, 80,81, 120, 121. While all the other bits are in place the state bit 121 is still at FF 121, if we use the swap sequence in **(C)**. Thus an additional mux is needed.

(F) Key Path: There are two issues in the key path. We need 4 S-box accesses which must be scheduled at cycles in which it is not used by the state pipeline. And we need to consider the effect of rotating the last column of the key state by one byte before applying S-box, adding round constant and adding it back to the first column. We take inputs to the S-box at cycles 112, 120, 128, 5 to avoid conflict with the state path and the output is written back three cycles later i.e. at cycles 115, 123, 0, 8. We always add the S-box output to content

Fig. 4: The sequential Mixcolumn Circuit.

of FFs 16 to 23 and write it back to FFs 15 to 22. In order to accommodate for the Rotword operation on the last key column, we take the S-box inputs from FFs 123 to 130 at $t = 112, 120, 128$, and FFs 91 to 98 at $t = 5$ (it is easy to check that this notionally rotates the last column by a byte before applying the S-box). The only other operations remaining in the key path are addition of the updated first column to the second, second to the third etc. This is done by executing $\text{FF}[32] = \text{FF}[32] + \text{FF}[0]$ at all $t < 96$, which is written to FF 31 in the next cycle.

5 Byte Serial Circuit

The byte serial circuit is probably the most efficient of the three AES circuits when we consider both area and latency parameters. There are numerous byte serial implementations of AES-128 present in literature. The first such circuit was proposed in [MPL⁺11], which computed one round in 21 cycles. Since the number of S-box accesses in one round of AES-128 is 20, then if the circuit uses a single S-box, this represents close to optimal latency. In [BBR16], the authors combined encryption and decryption into one circuit. [BBR17] improved the above work further by using the fact that the Mixcolumn matrix had multiplicative order 4. This obviated the need for inverse Mixcolumn circuit for decryption, since the same functionality could be achieved by running the Mixcolumn circuit thrice. [BCB21] proposed a 16-cycle per round implementation that however required 2 S-box circuits. In this paper we try to design a 20-cycle per round using a single masked S-box which therefore is theoretically optimal.

Fig. 5: The byte-serial AES-128 circuit. Note we only show the datapath of one share.

We represent pictorially the byte-serial circuit (only the datapath of one share) in Figure 5. The salient features of the circuit are as follows:

- (A) Four additional byte flip-flops:** Since we aim to design a 20-cycle per round implementation, we add four additional byte flip-flops (BFFs) to accommodate this.
- (B) S-box Operations:** Consider an up-counter t modulo 20 that controls the data movement. At all $t < 16$, data is fed into the S-box after the roundkey addition operation i.e. via the signal on the wire leading to BFF 19. At $t \in [3, 18]$ the S-box output is written back to BFF 17.
- (C) Swaps in the state pipeline:** We perform the following swaps in the state pipeline

$$\text{swap}(10, 14) \text{ at } t \in \{11, 15, 19, 1\}$$

$$\text{swap}(3, 15) \text{ at } t \in \{0\}$$

$$\text{swap}(7, 15) \text{ at } t \in \{15, 19, 0\}$$

- (D) Combinatorial Mixcolumn:** Since all bits of a byte move together in a byte-serial circuit, there is no real advantage in using a sequential Mixcolumn

circuit. We use the combinatorial Mixcolumn circuit designed by [Max19] that uses only 92 XOR gates, connected to BFFs 0,4,8,12. The operation is performed at cycles $t \in \{0, 4, 8, 12\}$. The most significant byte is added to the next roundkey byte and cycled back 9 in the pipeline. The remaining bytes are written back to BFFs 0,1,2.

- (E) **Arrangement of Swaps:** As in the bit serial circuit, all the bytes are aligned in BFFs 0,4,8,12 at the instant when the Mixcolumn operation is activated with one exception. At $t = 0$, the byte indexed 15, is not present at BFF 3, if we execute the sequence of swaps outlined in (C). In stead it is present at BFF 15 at this instant. So we need one additional byte multiplexer to bring this byte to the Mixcolumn input port.
- (F) **Key Path:** We take inputs to the S-box at cycles 16,17,18,19 to avoid scheduling conflict with the state path and the output is written back three cycles later i.e. at cycles 19,0,1,2. We always add the S-box output to content of BFF 1 and write it back to BFF 0 in the next cycle. In order to accommodate for the Rotword operation on the last key column, we take the S-box inputs from BFF 17 at $t = 16, 17, 18$, and BFF 13 at $t = 19$ (it is easy to check that this notionally rotates the last column by a byte before applying the S-box). The only other operations remaining in the key path are addition of the updated first column to the second, second to the third etc. This is done by executing $\text{BFF}[4] = \text{BFF}[4] + \text{BFF}[0]$ at all $t < 12$ and the result is written to BFF 3 in the next cycle.

6 Round Based Circuit

Fig. 6: The round-based AES-128 circuit. Note we only show the datapath of one share.

The round based circuit is simplest to describe since the circuit for processing one round in a single clock cycle is already available, and one just needs to iterate over 10 cycles for the result. In this case however, one encryption operation needs 31 cycles, since each S-box computation needs 3 cycles as shown in Figure 2. The circuit for one share of the round based circuit is shown in Figure 6. Although the circuit needs 31 cycles to do one encryption, it can encrypt 3 plaintexts in the first 33 cycles. It can be seen that the register stages used for the S-box operation form a natural pipeline, and so if three plaintext/key pairs are input to the circuit at $t = 0/1/2$ successively, the result can be obtained from the circuit at $t = 31/32/33$ respectively.

7 Implementation Results

We synthesized all the ciphers using the Nangate 15nm, TSMC 65 nm and UMC 40nm standard cell libraries. All the designs were initially implemented in VHDL their functionality has been verified using Mentor Graphics ModelSim SE. The designs were synthesized using the Synopsys Design Compiler using the `compile_ultra -no_autoungroup -no_boundary_optimization` command. The switching activity was collected while performing a timing simulation on the synthesized netlist using Synopsys VCS. The switching activity was then back annotated to estimate the power consumption using Synopsys Power Compiler. Table 2, reports the result of our implementations. Since the a large part of the design is the masked s-box, it can be seen that the byte serial design offers the most in terms of area-throughput ratio.

#	Architecture	Area (μm^2)		#Random Bits	#Cycles	Power (mW)	Energy (nJ)
Nangate 15 nm							
1	Bit-Serial	2392.4	12168	40000	1441	0.1413	20.36
	Byte-Serial	2808.7	14286		220	0.2010	4.42
	Round-Based	34926.1	177643		31	1.0071	3.12
TSMC 65 nm							
2	Bit-Serial	14908.0	10353		1441	0.5686	81.93
	Byte-Serial	17401.0	12084		220	0.7138	15.70
	Round-Based	227506.7	157991		31	7.0350	21.81
UMC 40 nm							
3	Bit-Serial	6019.0	10968		1441	0.2107	30.37
	Byte-Serial	7016.1	12784		220	0.3670	8.74
	Round-Based	87793.5	159974		31	1.6400	5.08

Table 2: Synthesis results for the three AES-128 architectures. Note that power has been evaluated at 10 MHz.

8 Conclusion

Starting from the observation that Time Share masking is significantly more efficient in masking smaller degree S-boxes, we put this premise to test by using the power map decomposition of the AES S-box. We found that the standalone S-box occupied almost half the area when the internal inverse map is decomposed into lower degree power maps. We then tried to fit this masked S-box into the pipeline of a bit-serial, byte-serial and round-based circuit. As a result we get fairly compact masked implementation of AES-128 in around 12 kGE, 14kGE and 177 kGE across three standard cell libraries.

Acknowledgment: The authors wish to thank all the reviewers whose feedback helped improve the paper. The research presented in this paper was partially funded by the European Union, by grant No. 101135183 (MYRTUS). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- BBR16. Subhadeep Banik, Andrey Bogdanov, and Francesco Regazzoni. Atomic-aes: A compact implementation of the AES encryption/decryption core. In Orr Dunkelman and Somitra Kumar Sanadhya, editors, *Progress in Cryptology - INDOCRYPT 2016 - 17th International Conference on Cryptology in India, Kolkata, India, December 11-14, 2016, Proceedings*, volume 10095 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 173–190, 2016.
- BBR17. Subhadeep Banik, Andrey Bogdanov, and Francesco Regazzoni. Compact Circuits for Combined AES Encryption/Decryption. *Journal of Cryptographic Engineering*, pages 1–15, 2017.
- BCB21. Fatih Balli, Andrea Caforio, and Subhadeep Banik. The area-latency symbiosis: Towards improved serial encryption circuits. *IACR Trans. Cryptogr. Hardw. Embed. Syst.*, 2021(1):239–278, 2021.
- BCO04. Eric Brier, Christophe Clavier, and Francis Olivier. Correlation power analysis with a leakage model. In Marc Joye and Jean-Jacques Quisquater, editors, *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems – CHES 2004*, volume 3156 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 16–29, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, August 11–13, 2004. Springer, Heidelberg, Germany.
- BGN⁺14. Begül Bilgin, Benedikt Gierlichs, Svetla Nikova, Ventzislav Nikov, and Vincent Rijmen. Higher-order threshold implementations. In Palash Sarkar and Tetsu Iwata, editors, *Advances in Cryptology – ASIACRYPT 2014, Part II*, volume 8874 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 326–343, Kaoshiung, Taiwan, R.O.C., December 7–11, 2014. Springer, Heidelberg, Germany.
- CS20. Gaëtan Cassiers and François-Xavier Standaert. Trivially and efficiently composing masked gadgets with probe isolating non-interference. *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, 15:2542–2555, 2020.
- DNR19. Siemen Dhooghe, Svetla Nikova, and Vincent Rijmen. Threshold implementations in the robust probing model. In Begül Bilgin, Svetla Petkova-Nikova,

- and Vincent Rijmen, editors, *Proceedings of ACM Workshop on Theory of Implementation Security, TIS@CCS 2019, London, UK, November 11, 2019*, pages 30–37. ACM, 2019.
- GIB18. Hannes Groß, Rinat Iusupov, and Roderick Bloem. Generic low-latency masking in hardware. *IACR Trans. Cryptogr. Hardw. Embed. Syst.*, 2018(2):1–21, 2018.
- GMK16. Hannes Groß, Stefan Mangard, and Thomas Korak. Domain-oriented masking: Compact masked hardware implementations with arbitrary protection order. In Begül Bilgin, Svetla Nikova, and Vincent Rijmen, editors, *Proceedings of the ACM Workshop on Theory of Implementation Security, TIS@CCS 2016 Vienna, Austria, October, 2016*, page 3. ACM, 2016.
- ISW03. Yuval Ishai, Amit Sahai, and David Wagner. Private circuits: Securing hardware against probing attacks. In Dan Boneh, editor, *Advances in Cryptology – CRYPTO 2003*, volume 2729 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 463–481, Santa Barbara, CA, USA, August 17–21, 2003. Springer, Heidelberg, Germany.
- JMPS17. Jérémy Jean, Amir Moradi, Thomas Peyrin, and Pascal Sasdrich. Bit-sliding: A generic technique for bit-serial implementations of spn-based primitives - applications to aes, PRESENT and SKINNY. In Wieland Fischer and Naofumi Homma, editors, *Cryptographic Hardware and Embedded Systems - CHES 2017 - 19th International Conference, Taipei, Taiwan, September 25-28, 2017, Proceedings*, volume 10529 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 687–707. Springer, 2017.
- KJJ99. Paul C. Kocher, Joshua Jaffe, and Benjamin Jun. Differential power analysis. In Michael J. Wiener, editor, *Advances in Cryptology – CRYPTO’99*, volume 1666 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 388–397, Santa Barbara, CA, USA, August 15–19, 1999. Springer, Heidelberg, Germany.
- KSM20. David Knichel, Pascal Sasdrich, and Amir Moradi. SILVER - statistical independence and leakage verification. In Shiho Moriai and Huaxiong Wang, editors, *Advances in Cryptology - ASIACRYPT 2020 - 26th International Conference on the Theory and Application of Cryptology and Information Security, Daejeon, South Korea, December 7-11, 2020, Proceedings, Part I*, volume 12491 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 787–816. Springer, 2020.
- Max19. Alexander Maximov. AES mixcolumn with 92 XOR gates. *IACR Cryptol. ePrint Arch.*, page 833, 2019.
- MPL⁺11. Amir Moradi, Axel Poschmann, San Ling, Christof Paar, and Huaxiong Wang. Pushing the Limits: A Very Compact and a Threshold Implementation of AES. In Kenneth G. Paterson, editor, *Advances in Cryptology – EUROCRYPT 2011*, pages 69–88, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- MS16. Amir Moradi and François-Xavier Standaert. Moments-correlating dpa. In *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM Workshop on Theory of Implementation Security*, pages 5–15, 2016.
- NRS11. Svetla Nikova, Vincent Rijmen, and Martin Schlaffer. Secure hardware implementation of nonlinear functions in the presence of glitches. *Journal of Cryptology*, 24(2):292–321, April 2011.
- RBN⁺15. Oscar Reparaz, Begül Bilgin, Svetla Nikova, Benedikt Gierlichs, and Ingrid Verbauwhede. Consolidating masking schemes. In Rosario Gennaro and Matthew Robshaw, editors, *Advances in Cryptology - CRYPTO 2015 - 35th Annual Cryptology Conference, Santa Barbara, CA, USA, August 16-20, 2015*,

- Proceedings, Part I*, volume 9215 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 764–783. Springer, 2015.
- tsm. Time share masking, available at <https://github.com/KULeuven-COSIC/TSM>.
- VDB⁺24. Dilip Kumar S. V., Siemen Dhooghe, Josep Balasch, Benedikt Gierlichs, and Ingrid Verbauwhede. Time sharing - A novel approach to low-latency masking. *IACR Trans. Cryptogr. Hardw. Embed. Syst.*, 2024(3):249–272, 2024.
- WMM20. Felix Wegener, Lauren De Meyer, and Amir Moradi. Spin me right round rotational symmetry for fpga-specific AES: extended version. *J. Cryptol.*, 33(3):1114–1155, 2020.

Appendix A: Python script for keeping track of state

```

1 def rotate(S, newb):
2     for i in range(130):
3         S[i] = S[i + 1]
4     S[130] = newb
5
6 def show(x,r,i):
7     print("Round ",r," cycle",i)
8     l= [x[num] for num in range(0,8)]+[x[num] for num in
9         range(32,40)] + [x[num] for num in range(64,72)] + [x[num]
10        ] for num in range(96,104)]
11     print (l)
12     l= [x[num] for num in range(8,16)]+[x[num] for num in range
13        (40,48)] + [x[num] for num in range(72,80)] + [x[num] for
14        num in range(104,112)]
15     print (l)
16     l= [x[num] for num in range(16,24)]+[x[num] for num in
17        range(48,56)] + [x[num] for num in range(80,88)] + [x[num]
18        ] for num in range(112,120)]
19     print (l)
20     l= [x[num] for num in range(24,32)]+[x[num] for num in
21        range(56,64)] + [x[num] for num in range(88,96)] + [x[num]
22        ] for num in range(120,128)]
23     print (l)
24
25     l= [x[num] for num in range(128,131)]
26     print (l)
27
28 State = ['x'] * 131
29 B = [0]*128
30 for i in range(128):
31     B[i] = 'b%03d' % i
32
33 for round in range(2):
34     for i in range(131):

```

```

27
28     if (round==1 and (i==0 or i==32 or i==64 or i==96)):
29         show(State,round,i)
30     if i < 128 and round == 0:
31         newbit = B[i]
32     elif i >= 128 and round == 0:
33         newbit = '0000'
34     else:
35         newbit = State[0]
36
37     if (i >= 59 and i < 67) or (i >= 91 and i < 99) or (i >=
123 ) or (i >= 8 and i < 16):
38         t = State[80]
39         State[80] = State[112]
40         State[112] = t
41
42     if (i >= 91 and i < 99) or (i >= 123 ) or (i >= 0 and i <
8):
43         t = State[56]
44         State[56] = State[120]
45         State[120] = t
46
47     if (i==130 or (i >= 0 and i < 8)) :
48         t = State[25]
49         State[25] = State[121]
50         State[121] = t
51
52     rotate(State, newbit)

```

Appendix B: Mathematics of composition of Power maps

It can be seen that if we compose two power maps $x \rightarrow x^a$ and $x \rightarrow x^b$ over any characteristic 2 field $GF(2^c)$, the resultant power map is given by $x \rightarrow x^{a \times b \bmod 2^c - 1}$. This is naturally because the multiplicative group of $GF(2^c)$ has order $2^c - 1$, and so the above follows from Fermat's law. Note that all the integers in the set $[0, 2^c - 2]$ can be naturally partitioned with respect to the relation R defined thus:

$$(a, b) \in R, \text{ if } \exists t, \text{ such that } a \equiv b \cdot 2^t \bmod (2^c - 1)$$

This is an equivalence relation, and thus partitions the set $[0, 2^c - 2]$. these partitions are well studied in mathematical literature and are more well known by the name cyclotomic cosets. For example the cyclotomic cosets modulo $2^4 - 1 = 15$ are

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_0 &= \{0\}, C_1 = \{1, 2, 4, 8\} \\
 C_3 &= \{3, 6, 12, 9\}, C_5 = \{5, 10\} \\
 C_7 &= \{7, 14, 13, 11\}
 \end{aligned}$$

The smallest entries of the cyclotomic cosets are called coset representatives. Note each coset is sub-scripted by the representative. Moreover the entire coset can be generated by successively multiplying the representative by 2 and reducing modulo $2^c - 1$. The following lemma can be easily proven.

Lemma 1. *All elements of in a single coset have same hamming weight when seen as a binary string. In fact all elements in a single coset are finite rotations of one another.*

Proof. This fact is easily borne out by the example above. For example, C_3 when viewed as a set of binary strings can be written as $\{0011, 0110, 1100, 1001\}$. Let $a \in C_i$, for some i . If $2a < 2^c - 1$, then it is obvious that there is no overflow and so a and $2a$ do have the same weight and are rotations of one another. If $b = 2a \geq 2^c - 1$, note that $2^c \equiv 1 \pmod{2^c - 1}$, and that the msb of a equals 1. Consider \ll, \lll to be the left-shift, left-rotate over c -bit words. In that case $b = 2a = (a \ll 1) + 2^c$, where $(a \ll 1)$, is simply the c -bit representation of a left shifted by 1. The overflowing bit is represented by the addition of 2^c . Reducing modulo $2^c - 1$, we have $b \equiv (a \ll 1) + 1 \pmod{2^c - 1} \equiv (a \lll 1) \pmod{2^c - 1}$ which is what we need to prove. The equality of hamming weight immediately follows.

The following are also easy to see/prove

- A:** Since $x \rightarrow x^{2^t}$ are linear maps over characteristic 2 fields, all elements in a single coset represent affine equivalent power maps. That is if $a, b \in C_i$ for some i , then $x \rightarrow x^a$ and $x \rightarrow x^b$ are affine equivalent maps.
- B:** Since we have already proven that all elements of a single coset are bit-rotations of each other, this immediately gives us the number of cosets modulo $2^c - 1$. This is just the number of length c necklaces over the binary alphabet minus 1, since the all one string is equivalent to the all 0 string modulo $2^c - 1$. It is a well known fact in combinatorics that there are $M(c) = \frac{1}{c} \sum_{d|c} \phi(d) 2^{c/d}$ different binary necklaces of length c , where $\phi()$ is the Euler totient function. So the number of cosets is given by $M(c) - 1$, and the number of non-zero cosets is $M(c) - 2$.

Group Operation

We try to define an operation \odot between 2 cosets as follows. Let $a \in C_i$ and $b \in C_j$ for some i, j . Now let $p = a \cdot b \pmod{2^c - 1}$ and $p \in C_k$ for some k . Then we claim that for any arbitrary $a^* \in C_i$ and $b^* \in C_j$, $p^* = a^* \cdot b^* \pmod{2^c - 1} \in C_k$. Indeed this is true since

$$\begin{aligned} a^* \cdot b^* &\equiv a \cdot 2^t \cdot b \cdot 2^s \pmod{2^c - 1} \equiv a \cdot b \cdot 2^{t+s} \pmod{2^c - 1} \\ &\equiv p \cdot 2^{t+s} \pmod{2^c - 1} \in C_k \text{ as required.} \end{aligned}$$

So this naturally gives rise to the operation \odot , between two cosets. $C_i \odot C_j = C_k$ if the product modulo $2^c - 1$ of any element of C_i , and any element of C_j , lies

in C_k . This sometimes gives rise to a group structure among the set of cosets, especially if $2^c - 1$ is prime, because then it guarantees the existence of an inverse for each element and thus also each coset. Note that since modular multiplication is associative and commutative, the coset operation is also associative and commutative. And the coset in which 1 lies, can serve as the identity element. For example, when $c = 7$, $2^c - 1 = 127$ is a prime number. All the 18 non-zero cosets modulo 127 form a group. For $c = 4$, the cosets that don't have divisors of 15, i.e. C_1, C_7 forms a group of 2 elements. But $2^8 - 1 = 255$ is not a prime. So the group structure of these cosets is slightly tricky.

As can be seen in Table 3, over $GF(2^8)$, not all the 35 cosets are in the Group defined by \odot . There are 16 elements in the group (marked in cyan background in the above table), and it has 2 cyclic subgroups generated by the elements C_7 of order 8, and C_{127} of order 2. Hence all cosets can be factored as $C_7^x \odot C_{127}^y$, where $x \in [0, 7]$ and $y \in [0, 1]$. In the paper we use the fact that $C_{13} \odot C_{49} = C_7^6 \odot C_{127} \odot C_7^2 = C_{127}$, which leads to the decomposition of the inverse map $x \rightarrow x^{254}$ into the power maps $x \rightarrow x^{26}$ and $x \rightarrow x^{49}$. However all the Hamming weight 2 cosets contain either divisors of 255, or integers that are not co-prime with 255, hence they don't have inverses. Hence these cosets are not part of the group. This means that no matter how many quadratic power maps we combine we will not reach the inverse map over $GF(2^8)$.

Rep	Coset	HW	Remark
C_0	0	0	Null
C_1	1,2,4,8,16,32,64,128	1	Identity
C_3	3,6,12,24,48,96,129,192	2	*
C_5	5,10,20,40,65,80,130,160	2	*
C_7	7,14,28,56,112,131,193,224	3	C_7
C_9	9,18,33,36,66,72,132,144	2	*
C_{11}	11,22,44,88,97,133,176,194	3	C_7^3
C_{13}	13,26,52,67,104,134,161,208	3	$C_7^6 \odot C_{127}$
C_{15}	15,30,60,120,135,195,225,240	4	*
C_{17}	17,34,68,136	2	*
C_{19}	19,38,49,76,98,137,152,196	3	C_7^2
C_{21}	21,42,69,81,84,138,162,168	3	*
C_{23}	23, 46, 92, 113, 139, 184, 197, 226	4	$C_7^5 \odot C_{127}$
C_{25}	25, 35, 50, 70, 100, 140, 145, 200	4	*
C_{27}	27, 54, 99, 108, 141, 177, 198, 216	4	*
C_{29}	29, 58, 71, 116, 142, 163, 209, 232	4	C_7^5
C_{31}	31, 62, 124, 143, 199, 227, 241, 248	5	$C_7 \odot C_{127}$
C_{37}	37, 41, 73, 74, 82, 146, 148, 164	3	C_7^7
C_{39}	39, 57, 78, 114, 147, 156, 201, 228	4	*
C_{43}	43, 86, 89, 101, 149, 172, 178, 202	4	$C_7^4 \odot C_{127}$
C_{45}	45, 75, 90, 105, 150, 165, 180, 210	4	*
C_{47}	47, 94, 121, 151, 188, 203, 229, 242	5	C_7^6
C_{51}	51, 102, 153, 204	4	*
C_{53}	53, 77, 83, 106, 154, 166, 169, 212	4	C_7^4
C_{55}	55, 110, 115, 155, 185, 205, 220, 230	5	*
C_{59}	59, 103, 118, 157, 179, 206, 217, 236	5	$C_7^2 \odot C_{127}$
C_{61}	61, 79, 122, 158, 167, 211, 233, 244	5	$C_7^3 \odot C_{127}$
C_{63}	63, 126, 159, 207, 231, 243, 249, 252	6	*
C_{85}	85, 170	4	*
C_{87}	87, 93, 117, 171, 174, 186, 213, 234	5	*
C_{91}	91, 107, 109, 173, 181, 182, 214, 218	5	$C_7^7 \odot C_{127}$
C_{95}	95, 125, 175, 190, 215, 235, 245, 250	6	*
C_{111}	111, 123, 183, 189, 219, 222, 237, 246	6	*
C_{119}	119, 187, 221, 238	6	*
C_{127}	127, 191, 223, 239, 247, 251, 253, 254	7	C_{127}

Table 3: All cyclotomic cosets modulo 255